

ROBOSAT Data Management Plan for Autonomous robot navigation in the wild using satellite-based 3D geographical information

Version 1

Description

ROBOSAT aims to develop a scalable platform for autonomous data collection in unstructured environments using a quadrupedal robot equipped with multi-modal sensors (cameras, LiDAR, IMU, GNSS and raw I/Q data acquisition). The project combines satellite-based 3D geographic information systems (GIS), GNSS, robotics and AI to create high-quality datasets, advanced data management tools and improved localisation algorithms. The project will produce open scientific data and software to support research and innovation in robotics, navigation and environmental monitoring. This document

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Autonomous robot navigation
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Researchers

Elena Simona Lohan (0000-0003-1718-6924), Joaquín Torres-Sospedra (0000-0003-4338-4334), Irina Mocanu (0000-0001-5176-9344), Marco Hutter (0000-0002-4285-4990), Yelyzaveta Pervysheva (0009-0009-7676-0851), Andrei Cramariuc (0000-0002-9301-0253), Muhammad Safi (0009-0009-4719-2226), William Talbot (0009-0008-9426-3595), Alina SANDU (0000-0001-7946-2109), Imad Alex Awada (0000-0002-5783-2428), Andrei Mocanu (0000-0002-6608-9349), Dragoi Marius (0000-0002-5240-8505), José M. Claver (0000-0002-9617-3453), Esther Dura (0000-0002-2603-5549), Miguel Matey-Sanz (0000-0002-1189-5079), Ignacio Miralles (0000-0002-1205-5434)

Organizations

Tampere University, University of Valencia, ETH Zurich, CENTRUL
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1. Basic Information

Title: ROBOSAT Data Management Plan for Autonomous robot navigation in the wild using satellite-based 3D geographical information

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ROBOSAT aims to develop a scalable platform for autonomous data collection in unstructured environments using a quadrupedal robot equipped with multi-modal sensors (cameras, LiDAR, IMU, GNSS and raw I/Q data acquisition). The project combines satellite-based 3D geographic information systems (GIS), GNSS, robotics and AI to create high-quality datasets, advanced data management tools and improved localisation algorithms. The project will produce open scientific data and software to support research and innovation in robotics, navigation and environmental monitoring. This document

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Affiliations:

Tampere University
University of Valencia
ETH Zurich
CENTRUL IT PENTRU STIINTA SI TEHNOLOGIE SRL

Contact: Lohan Elena Simona (elena-simona.lohan@tuni.fi), Cramariuc Andrei (crandrei@ethz.ch), Mocanu Irina (irina.mocanu@citst.ro), Torres-Sospedra Joaquin (Joaquin.Torres@uv.es)

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4. Generic Data Questions

Descriptions

CHIST-ERA Data Management - Generic Questions

ROBOSAT aims to develop a scalable platform for autonomous data collection in unstructured environments using a quadrupedal robot equipped with multi-modal sensors (cameras, LiDAR, IMU, GNSS and raw I/Q data acquisition). The project combines satellite-based 3D geographic information systems (GIS), GNSS, robotics and AI to create high-quality datasets, advanced data management tools and improved localisation algorithms. The project will produce open scientific data and software to support research and innovation in robotics, navigation and environmental monitoring.

This document presents the Data Management Plan (DMP) for the ROBOSAT project, outlining the key principles governing data management within the project consortium in relation to research data. It describes the data lifecycle, including the types of data

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generated and the applicable Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) considerations. The plan addresses how data will be generated, stored, maintained, and updated throughout the project, as well as the standards and procedures for data sharing and reuse. The DMP will function as a living document, to be periodically updated by the project partners in order to reflect any significant changes in data management practices during the course of the project.

Template: [CHIST-ERA Data Management - Generic Questions](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Documentation And Data Quality

1.1 Documentation And Data Quality

1.1.1 What metadata and documentation will accompany the data?

1.1.1.1 Indicate how the data will be organised during the project

ROBOSAT will generate heterogeneous and multi-modal datasets combining robotic sensor data, satellite-based GIS information, and GNSS measurements. To ensure data usability and long-term reusability, all datasets will be accompanied by clear documentation and metadata describing their origin, structure, processing steps, and intended use.

Data will be structured in folders, where each folder will be linked to a measurement campaign. The name for the folder will include the scenario and date. The folder will store different files, one for each sensors o capture system.

1.1.1.2 Consider what other documentation is needed to enable re-use

Documentation will include:1) Data dictionaries and README files describing dataset structure, variables, units, and acquisition conditions.

2) Description of experimental setups, sensors used, calibration procedures, and software versions.

3) Metadata describing acquisition time, location, sensor configuration, and processing pipelines.

4) Links between raw data, processed data, and associated software tools.

1.1.1.3 Consider how this information will be captured and where it will be recorded

Preliminary experiments will include measurements with the GNSS logger and other devices to understand the measured data. The final datasets will be collected with the Anymal platform developed at ETH Zurich on mountains and forest. The Anymal platform will collect raw images, 3D point and I/Q binary data, which will be stored in rosbag. Collected data will be offloaded to local computers where it will be uploaded to the dedicated servers hosted at the University of València.

1.1.2 What data quality control measures will be used?

1.1.2.1 Explain how the consistency and quality of data collection will be controlled and documented

- Standardised data capture
- Peer review of data
- Other

Each measurement campaign will be manually controlled and documented. We will provide a report summary for each campaign with the main statistics linked to each sensor type.

2 Reused Data

2.1 Reused Data

2.1.1 State any constraints on re-use of existing data if there are any

ROBOSAT builds upon existing open datasets and geospatial resources in order to complement the data collected during the project and to enable large-scale analysis and benchmarking.

The project will reuse data from established open repositories, including:

- 1) Copernicus Sentinel satellite imagery and related geospatial products.
- 2) National Land Survey (NLS) and other open-access topographic and geographic datasets.
- 3) Publicly available GIS layers and environmental maps relevant to the deployment areas.

All reused datasets will retain their original licenses and attribution requirements. The consortium will ensure compliance with license conditions and will document provenance information for all reused data.

2.1.2 Briefly state the reasons if the re-use of any existing data sources has been considered but discarded

The reuse of existing data serves multiple purposes:

- 1) Providing contextual geographic information to complement locally collected robotic sensor data.
- 2) Supporting data fusion between satellite-based and ground-based observations.

3) Enabling reproducibility and comparison with existing research.

4) Metadata records will explicitly distinguish between newly generated data and externally sourced datasets. Links to original repositories and citation instructions will be included in the documentation to ensure traceability and proper attribution.

Whenever possible, reused data will be integrated using interoperable formats and standard metadata schemas to facilitate reuse within and beyond the project.

3 Storage And Backup During The Research Process

3.1 Storage And Backup During The Research Process

3.1.1 How will data and metadata be stored and backed up during the research?

3.1.1.1 Describe where the data will be stored and backed up during research activities and how often the backup will be performed

NASROBOSAT

Other

During the project, data will be stored using secure institutional storage systems at UVEG and collaborative research infrastructures provided by the consortium partners. Given the large volume of multi-modal sensor data generated by ROBOSAT, storage solutions will combine two dedicated local high-performance storage systems at UV and the Node Tirant of the Spanish Supercomputing Network. The NAS system has a RAID5 setup with two spare disks (<https://robonas.uv.es>) with a tape-based backup in the Node Tirant.

3.1.2 How will data security and protection of sensitive data be taken care of during the research?

3.1.2.2 Explain which institutional data protection policies are in place

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The data will be encrypted on the NAS and protected by a firewall.

4 Legal And Ethical Requirements, Codes Of Conduct

4.1 Legal And Ethical Requirements, Codes Of Conduct

4.1.1 Personal data

4.1.1.1 Are there any personal data to be formulated?

No

4.1.2 How will other legal issues, such as intellectual property rights and ownership, be managed? What legislation is applicable?

4.1.2.1 Data ownership and accessibility

4.1.2.1.1 Who will be the owner(s) of the data?

University of Valencia

Joaquín Torres-Sospedra (0000-0003-4338-4334)

Main data will be stored at UV

4.1.2.1.2 Explain what access or restrictions will apply to the data?

Open

No restrictions to the data to be provided in open access via CC4-BY licenses

4.1.2.2 Intellectual property rights

4.1.2.2.1 Explain which intellectual property and how will they be dealt with

Other

The consortium has preliminary agreed that the results are to be owned by the Party/-s that generated them. We will grant royalty free licences for use, development and wider non commerial application of database and software.

Regarding commercial application, access rights to results if needed for exploitation of a party's own results shall be granted on fair and reasonable conditions. Each unit will be responsible for ensuring their compliance with the provisions of the GA and CA, as well as for the protection of their own (and other partners') Results and Background. Researchers will have the right to publish research results with a reasonable period of notification of publication. Copies of any conference papers, articles, etc. will be provided in advance to the MB who will inform the PIs and other interested parties (e.g., external co-authors). Any of the parties may object to the publication within 15 days. Each unit will be responsible for ensuring their compliance with the provisions of the CA and their national GA as well as for the protection of their own (and other partners') Background.

4.1.3 Ethical issues

4.1.3.1 What ethical issues and codes of conduct are there, and how will they be taken into account?

- Legal issues such as IP rights
- Other

ROBOSAT will comply with all relevant legal, ethical, and regulatory requirements related to data management throughout the project lifecycle. The project does not intentionally collect personal or sensitive data. The primary data sources consist of robotic sensor measurements, geospatial information, and environmental observations. However, incidental capture of personal data (e.g., individuals appearing in images during outdoor data collection) cannot be fully excluded. In case personal data will be collected, all research protocols involving personal user data will undergo ethical review. In addition, we will apply anonymization and aggregation techniques before storing or sharing data; we will implement GDPR-compliant consent procedures for any human-related data; and we will use end-to-end encryption for data transmission and storage.

To address potential legal and ethical issues, the following measures will be applied:

- Compliance with applicable data protection regulations, including the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) where relevant.
- Ethical oversight within the consortium, coordinated through the project management structure.
- Implementation of procedures for anonymisation or removal of identifiable information if detected.
- Restriction or controlled access to datasets where legal or ethical concerns arise.

Data collection activities will be conducted in accordance with local laws and institutional ethical guidelines in each participating country. Ethical considerations related to AI usage, potential dual-use implications, and responsible research practices will be continuously monitored throughout the project. Whenever legal or ethical constraints prevent full data sharing, metadata will remain openly accessible, and conditions for potential access will be clearly described.

5 Data Sharing And Long-term Preservation

5.1 Data Sharing And Long-term Preservation

5.1.1 How and when will data be shared? Are there possible restrictions to data sharing or embargo reasons?

5.1.1.1 Explain how the data will be discoverable and shared

- Deposit in a FAIR-enabling data repository
- Use of a secure data service

5.1.1.2 Outline the plan for data preservation and give information on how long the data will be retained

Raw data will be made available at least 3-5 years beyond the project lifetime.

Data used in experiments reported in scientific papers will be made available in a FAIR-enabling data repository like zenodo.

5.1.1.3 Explain when the data will be made available

The data will be available after

5.1.1.4 Will exclusive use of the data be claimed?

No

5.1.1.7 Is it necessary to restrict access to certain communities or to apply a data sharing agreement?

Yes

5.1.2 How will data for preservation be selected, and where data will be preserved long-term?

5.1.2.1 Describe the data to be preserved long-term

- Observational (e.g., sensor data, data from surveys)
- Derived or compiled (e.g., text mining, 3D models)

5.1.2.2 Indicate where the data will be deposited

The data will be hosted in a dedicated NAS system at UV with tape-based backup in Tirant, the node of the Spanish Network of Supercomputing.

Additional backups will be done at host units. Processed data used in scientific works will be deposited in Zenodo.

5.1.2.3 How will the data be effectively curated beyond the lifetime of the grant

Data generated during this project will be curated to ensure long-term accessibility, usability, and preservation beyond the lifetime of the grant. Upon completion of the project, all finalized datasets will be deposited in <https://robonas.uv.es>. A backup will be stored in the node Tirant of the Spanish Network of Supercomputing. Relevant data for project's outputs will be deposited in Zenodo. Zenodo provides persistent DOI, version control, and long-term storage infrastructure to ensure continued access.

The datasets will be accompanied by comprehensive metadata, documentation, and data dictionaries describing the methodology, variables, formats, and any processing steps used in the creation of the data. Files will be stored in widely used, non-proprietary formats where possible to ensure future usability.

Responsibility for maintaining the data will be transferred to UV's and principal investigator's at UV, both of which maintain policies and infrastructure for long-term data stewardship. Access permissions and licensing (e.g., open or restricted access where appropriate) will be clearly defined to facilitate reuse while protecting sensitive information when necessary.

Through repository preservation policies, standardized metadata, and open documentation, the data will remain discoverable, interpretable, and reusable by the broader research community well beyond the duration of the grant.

5.1.3 How will the application of a unique and persistent identifier to each data set be ensured?

5.1.3.1 What type of persistent identifier (PID) will be used?

DOI

6 Data Management Responsibilities And Resources

6.1 Data Management Responsibilities And Resources

6.1.1 Who will be responsible for data management?

6.1.1.1 Outline the roles and responsibilities for data management/stewardship activities

Joaquín Torres-Sospedra (0000-0003-4338-4334)

Joaquín will be the contact person at UV to store and maintain the raw data.

Storage and backup

6.1.1.2 Explain the co-ordination of data management responsibilities across partners

All Consortium partners will take due care of the own-collected data, in accordance with GDPR and national regulations at their own institutes. The joint data will be shared through UV NASROBOSAT servers and via Zenodo

5. Data Management

6. Software Management

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